

IPBES VA Chapter 2. Literature review on value articulating institutions / IPBES values assessment (2.4)

Code: IPBES_VA_2.4

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. One of the topics that the assessment has to cover is the impact of institutions on values at stake in decision-making processes. In order to do so, chapter 2 must provide the conceptual basis on the relations between values and institutions, particularly those institutions that articulate values. Section 2.4 covers this subject by presenting information retrieved from systematic reviews and complemented by additional information. This report explains the process for gathering that additional information, which consisted of four separate literature searches. This literature review is part of the stage 2 strategy that chapter 2 has incorporated to bring in different sources of evidence appropriate for each section and subsection.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** searches performed in one academic database and in Google Scholar to retrieve academic literature relevant to inform section 2.4 on value articulating institutions

Details of search 1:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** general search without restrictions for relevant publications performed on 28 July 2020 and repeated on 7 December 2020 to complement information
- **Search terms:**
TS= (TITLE-ABS-KEY (Value Articulating Institutions))
- **Search languages:** Non-restricted
- **Search engine:** Science Direct
- **Exact search date:** 28 July 2020 and repeated on 7 December 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 62 references
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.4_7-12-2020_(A).pdf

Details of search 2:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search for publications found in Google Scholar until the date of the search (30 September 2020)
- **Search terms:**
TS= (TITLE-ABS-KEY (cost-benefit analysis AND distributional weights) OR (cost-benefit analysis AND multicriteria analysis))
- **Search languages:** No restrictions
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Exact search date:** 30 September 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 5 references
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_2.4_30-9-2020_(B).pdf

Details of search 3:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search for publications found in Google Scholar until the date of the second search (4 December 2020)
- **Search terms:**
TS= (TITLE-ABS-KEY (integrated OR plural) AND (valuation))
- **Search languages:** No restrictions
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Exact search date:** 28 July 2020 and 4 December 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 8 references
- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_2.4_4-12-2020_(C).pdf

Details of search 4:

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Specific but non-systematic search for publications found in Google Scholar until the date of the search (27 July 2020)
- **Search terms:**
TS= (TITLE-ABS-KEY (reflexivity AND valuation))
- **Search languages:** No restrictions
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Exact search date:** 27 July 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 11 references
- **Location and format of the data (D):** IPBES_VA_2.4_27-7-2020_(D).pdf

The retrieved references were reviewed by the project leader. Based on expert knowledge, relevant information for section 2.4 of chapter 2 of the IPBES values assessment was selected.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.4_7-12-2020_(A)	pdf	142 KB	PDF with list of 62 references retrieved from search 1
B	IPBES_VA_2.4_30-9-2020_(B)	pdf	113 KB	PDF with list of 5 references retrieved from search 2
C	IPBES_VA_2.4_4-12-2020_(C)	pdf	119 KB	PDF with list of 8 references retrieved from search 3
D	IPBES_VA_2.4_27-7-2020_(D)	pdf	114 KB	PDF with list of 11 references retrieved from search 4